

Summer School on Extreme Temperature and Precipitation Events

Session 3: Floods

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Organization: Justus Liebig University Giessen - JLU

Cluj-Napoca, Romania

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1. Water cycle

Springer-Verlag GmbH Germany 2017
 Q. Duan et al. (eds.), Handbook of Hydrometeorological Ensemble Forecasting,
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-40457-3_22-1

1. Water cycle

Catchment

Catchment is area where all water, drains to same outlet.

<https://seawa.ca/your-watershed/what-is-a-watershed>

Precipitation

Measuring **rainfall** as a depth is an international standard mainly because it is very easy to convert depth to volume; The conversion factor is **1 mm of rainfall = 1 Liter of water/m²**

1 mm -> 1 mm/day

$$i = \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta t} \left[\frac{mm}{hr} \right]$$

$$i = \frac{5 \text{ mm}}{1 \text{ day}} = 0.208 \frac{mm}{hr}$$

<https://eiccontrols.com/en/inicio/224-sensor-inteligente-davis-02-mm-para-mediciones-de-precipitaciones.html>

Evaporation, transpiration, and evapotranspiration

https://abronexports.com/Open_Pan_Evaporimeter_Round_measuring_10mt2_with_pule_GI_or_copper_also_she_et_Big_with_measuring__meteorology_AM-311GI.htm

Miralles, D. G., De Jeu, R. A. M., Gash, J. H., Holmes, T. R. H., & Dolman, A. J. (2011). Magnitude and variability of land evaporation and its components at the global scale. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 15(3), 967–981.

Infiltration

[https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Infiltration_\(Hydrogeologie\)](https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Infiltration_(Hydrogeologie))

<https://bssjearthscience.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/12/unit-7-review-not-mine.pdf>

Streamflow

Streamflow, discharge, or runoff is the portion of rainfall, snowmelt or irrigation water that runs over the soil surface toward the stream channel.

$$Q = A \bar{u}$$

- **Q** is the discharge ($[L^3T^{-1}]$; m³/s or ft³/s)
- **A** is the cross-sectional area of the portion of the channel occupied by the flow ($[L^2]$; m² or ft²)
- **u** is the average flow velocity ($[LT^{-1}]$; m/s or ft/s)

©The COMET Program

https://www.faculty.luther.edu/~bernatzr/RainfallRunoff/comet/hydro/basic/Runoff/print_version/04-soilproperties.htm

<https://canyonmag.net/technical/safety/hydrology/>

<https://www.knowyourh2o.com/outdoor-4/streamflow-measurement>

Water Balance

$$I - O = \Delta S$$

On basis Reynolds transport theorem (Law of conservation mass, law of conservation of linear momentum, law of conservation energy)

Water Balance

https://www.tripadvisor.de/Attraction_Review-g488181-d2487783-Reviews-Laguna_Quilotoa-Cotopaxi_Province.html

Δ net change in storage = $I + P + G_1 - E + G_0 + O$

stream inflow to lake precipitation evaporation groundwater inflow groundwater outflow stream water outflow

Why modelling ?

The use of models allows the stakeholder and decision makers to take descions on basis of limited measurements and qualitative predictions in space and time of the hydrological procceses.

Modelling is a fundamental and quantitative way to understand and analyze complex systems and phenomena.

Modelling is a complement to theory and experiments.

For example: evaluating the water availabilty for human consumption, floods, droughts, irrigation, water contamination and others.

https://www.hydrotech-group.com/blog/the-10-most-beautiful-water-dams-from-around-the-world

Type of models

Ochoa-Tocachi, Cuadros-Adriazola, Arapa, Aste, Ochoa-Tocachi, & Bonnesoeur. (2022). *Guide to Hydrologic Modeling*. Forest Trends Association. [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.forest-trends.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Guide-to-Hydrologic-Modeling-of-NI.pdf](https://www.forest-trends.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Guide-to-Hydrologic-Modeling-of-NI.pdf)

The GR4J Hydrological model

Si $P_k \geq E$, alors $P_n = P_k - E$ et $E_n = 0$,
Si $P_k < E$, alors $P_n = 0$ et $E_n = E - P_k$

$$Ps = \frac{X1 \cdot (1 - (\frac{S_k}{X1})^2) \cdot \tanh(\frac{Pn}{X1})}{1 + \frac{S_k}{X1} \cdot \tanh(\frac{Pn}{X1})} \text{ et } Es = \frac{S_k \cdot (2 - \frac{S_k}{X1}) \cdot \tanh(\frac{E_n}{X1})}{1 + (1 - \frac{S_k}{X1}) \cdot \tanh(\frac{E_n}{X1})}$$

$$S' = S_k + Ps - Es,$$

$$Perc = S' \cdot \left\{ 1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{4}{9} \cdot \frac{S'}{X1} \right)^4 \right]^{-1} \right\}, S_{k+1} = S' - Perc$$

$$Perc + (Pn - Ps)$$

$$\text{Si } 0 \leq j \leq X4, SH1(j) = \left(\frac{j}{X4}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}; \text{ Si } j > X4, SH1(j) = 1$$

$$\text{Si } 0 \leq j \leq X4, SH2(j) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{j}{X4}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}};$$

$$\text{Si } X4 \leq j \leq 2X4, SH2(j) = 1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(2 - \frac{j}{X4}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}};$$

$$\text{Si } j > 2X4, SH2(j) = 1$$

$$UH1(j) = SH1(j) - SH1(j-1)$$

$$UH2(j) = SH2(j) - SH2(j-1)$$

$$Q9(k) = 0.9 \cdot \sum_{j=1}^k UH1(j) \cdot Pr(k-j+1),$$

$$Q1(k) = 0.1 \cdot \sum_{j=1}^m UH2(j) \cdot Pr(k-j+1)$$

$$F = X2 \cdot \left(\frac{R_k}{X3}\right)^{\frac{2}{3}}; R' = \max(0; R_k + Q9(k) + F)$$

$$(DP) \begin{cases} Qr = R' \cdot \left\{ 1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{R'}{X3} \right)^4 \right]^{-1} \right\}; R_{k+1} = R' - Qr \\ Qd = \max(0; Q1(k) + F); \\ Q(k) = Qr + Qd \end{cases}$$

- X1 Capacity of the production store (mm)
- X2 Water exchange coefficient (mm)
- X3 Capacity of the nonlinear routing store (mm)
- X4 Unit hydrograph time base (day)

Perrin, C., Michel, C., & Andréassian, V. (2003). Improvement of a parsimonious model for streamflow simulation. *Journal of Hydrology*, 279(1-4), 275-289. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694\(03\)00225-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694(03)00225-7)

LISFLOOD

https://ec-jrc.github.io/lisflood-model/2_01_stdLISFLOOD_overview/

Long short-term memory models LSTM

$$z_t = \sigma(W_z \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t])$$

$$r_t = \sigma(W_r \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t])$$

$$\tilde{h}_t = \tanh(W \cdot [r_t * h_{t-1}, x_t])$$

$$h_t = (1 - z_t) * h_{t-1} + z_t * \tilde{h}_t$$

Kratzert, F., Klotz, D., Brenner, C., Schulz, K., and Herrnegger, M.: Rainfall–runoff modelling using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.*, 22, 6005–6022, <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-22-6005-2018>, 2018.

Feng, Z., Zhang, J., & Niu, W. (2024). A state-of-the-art review of long short-term memory models with applications in hydrology and water resources. *Applied Soft Computing*, 167, 112352. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2024.112352>

<https://colah.github.io/posts/2015-08-Understanding-LSTMs/#fnref1>

Protocol

Beven, K. J. (2012). *Rainfall-runoff modelling: The primer* (2nd ed.). Wiley-Blackwell.

He, M., Sandhu, P., Namadi, P., Reyes, E., Guivetchi, K., & Chung, F. (2025). Protocols for Water and Environmental Modeling Using Machine Learning in California. *Hydrology*, 12(3), 59. <https://doi.org/10.3390/hydrology12030059>

Data availability vs model complexity

Ochoa-Tocachi, Cuadros-Adriazola, Arapa, Aste, Ochoa-Tocachi, & Bonnesoeur. (2022). *Guide to Hydrologic Modeling*. Forest Trends Association. <https://www.forest-trends.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Guide-to-Hydrologic-Modeling-of-NI.pdf>

The inverse problem

We know X, and the inputs so we are interested to know the outputs

$$y = x_1 I + x_2$$

We know the inputs I, and the outputs y, so we are interested in the parameters.

$$y = x_1 I + x_2$$

Calibration, validation and performance evaluation

Ochoa-Tocachi, Cuadros-Adriazola, Arapa, Aste, Ochoa-Tocachi, & Bonnesoeur. (2022). *Guide to Hydrologic Modeling*. Forest Trends Association. [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.forest-trends.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Guide-to-Hydrologic-Modeling-of-NI.pdf](https://www.forest-trends.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Guide-to-Hydrologic-Modeling-of-NI.pdf)

Performance metric	Expression
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	$F_1 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N y_{s,t} - y_{o,t} $
Mean Square Error (MSE)	$F_2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N y_{s,t} - y_{o,t} ^2$
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	$F_3 = \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N y_{s,t} - y_{o,t} ^2 \right]^{1/2}$
Minimax objective function	$F_4 = \frac{1}{N} \max y_{s,t} - y_{o,t} $
Average Absolute Percentage Error (AAPE)	$F_5 = 100 \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \left \frac{y_{s,t} - y_{o,t}}{y_{o,t}} \right $
Mean Square Relative Error (MSRE)	$F_6 = 100 \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N \left \frac{y_{s,t} - y_{o,t}}{y_{o,t}} \right ^2$
Coefficient of determination (R^2)	$F_7 = \left\{ \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (y_{o,t} - \bar{y}_o)(y_{s,t} - \bar{y}_s)}{\left[\sum_{t=1}^N (y_{o,t} - \bar{y}_o)^2 \right]^{0.5} \left[\sum_{t=1}^N (y_{s,t} - \bar{y}_s)^2 \right]^{0.5}} \right\}^2$
Index of agreement (D)	$F_8 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (y_{s,t} - y_{o,t})^2}{\sum_{t=1}^N (y_{s,t} - \bar{y}_o + y_{o,t} - \bar{y}_o)^2}$
Nash–Sutcliffe Efficiency coefficient (NSE)	$F_9 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (y_{s,t} - y_{o,t})^2}{\sum_{t=1}^N (y_{o,t} - \bar{y}_o)^2}$

Biondi, D., Freni, G., Iacobellis, V., Mascaro, G., & Montanari, A. (2012). Validation of hydrological models: Conceptual basis, methodological approaches and a proposal for a code of practice. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts A/B/C*, 42–44, 70–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2011.07.037>

Modified Kling–Gupta efficiency $KGE' = 1 - \sqrt{(\gamma - 1)^2 + (\beta - 1)^2 + (r - 1)^2}$

Sensitivity and uncertainty analysis

Ochoa-Tocachi, Cuadros-Adriazola, Arapa, Aste, Ochoa-Tocachi, & Bonnesoeur. (2022). *Guide to Hydrologic Modeling*. Forest Trends Association. [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnllnibpccajpcgclefndmkaj/https://www.forest-trends.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Guide-to-Hydrologic-Modeling-of-NI.pdf](https://www.forest-trends.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Guide-to-Hydrologic-Modeling-of-NI.pdf)

Flow duration curves

A cumulative frequency curve that shows the percentage of time that specified discharges are equaled or exceeded

- Arrange flows in chronological order
- Find the number of records (N)
- Sort the data from highest to lowest
- Rank the data ($m=1$ for the highest value and $m=N$ for the lowest value)
- Compute exceedance probability for each value using the following formula
- Plot p on x axis and Q (sorted) on y axis

PDF fitting: Gumbel

- **Extreme Value Distribution:** Extreme value distributions are widely used in hydrology. Storm rainfalls are most commonly modeled by the **Extreme Value Type I distribution**. Below is the “cumulative” probability distribution version of the function.

$$F(x) = e^{-e^{-\left[\frac{x-u}{\alpha}\right]}} \quad -\infty \leq x \leq \infty$$

$$\alpha = \frac{\sqrt{6}s_x}{\pi}$$

$$u = \bar{x} - 0.5772\alpha$$

$$\text{Let } y = \frac{x-u}{\alpha}$$

- Correlating “y” with Return Period (T), the Extreme Value Distribution can be simplified to:

$$x_T = u + \alpha y_T$$

$$y_T = -\ln \left[\ln \left(\frac{T}{T-1} \right) \right]$$

$$(x-u) / \alpha = -\ln (-\ln (F(x)))$$

$$x = -\ln (-\ln (F(x))) \cdot \alpha + u$$

$$\mu_y = 0,5772; \sigma_y = 1,2825$$

$$\alpha = s_x / \sigma_y$$

$$u = \bar{x} - \mu_y \cdot \alpha$$

$$Pr = 1/Tr$$

Pr	Tr
[%]	[Years]
66.67	1.5
50	2
20	5
10	10
5	20
2	50
1	100
0.2	500
0.1	1 000
0.01	10 000

Chow VenTe, Maidment, David, R., Mays and Larry, W. (1988) Applied Hydrology. McGraw Hill, 277.

Ensemble forecasting

Ensembles

<https://www.rmets.org/metmatters/ensembles-how-forecast-comes-together>

Understanding the lead time

Hallouin, T., Bourgin, F., Perrin, C., Ramos, M.-H., & Andréassian, V. (2024). EvalHyd v0.1.2: A polyglot tool for the evaluation of deterministic and probabilistic streamflow predictions. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 17(11), 4561–4578. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-17-4561-2024>

Performance metrics for ensemble forecasting

Brier Score (BS)

$$BS = \overline{(p - o)^2}$$

Brier Skill Score (BSS)

Rank Probability Scores (RPS)

Continuous Ranked Probability Scores (CRPS)

Continuous Ranked Probability Skill Score (CRPSS)

Empirical CDF based on Ensemble

<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/FUG/Section+12.B+Statistical+Concepts+-+Probabilistic+Data>

Results analysis

What if ...

Ochoa-Tocachi, Cuadros-Adriazola, Arapa, Aste, Ochoa-Tocachi, & Bonnesoeur. (2022). *Guide to Hydrologic Modeling*. Forest Trends Association. [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://www.forest-trends.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Guide-to-Hydrologic-Modeling-of-NI.pdf](https://www.forest-trends.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/Guide-to-Hydrologic-Modeling-of-NI.pdf)

3. Example – DAKI

Methodology

1 Preparing the inputs:
Metorological forcings
 pd, rgd, tn, tx, ws, ta

1 Preparing the inputs:
Static maps

3 Setup and running

LISFLOOD

1 Preparing the inputs:
Hydrological observations
 Streamflow
 Station information

Observed streamflows

- [GRCD](#)
- <https://www.pegelportal.de/>

Qsim

4 Calibration

Calibrated Parameters (x14)

Qobs

5 Computing "pseudo-observations"

1arcmin-daily
1990 - 2021

1 STRENGTHENING THE RESEARCH CAPACITIES FOR EXTREME WEATHER EVENTS IN ROMANIA

Preparing the inputs:
Seasonal forecast reforecast

1deg-daily
1994 - 2015

Seasonal forecast + AI downscaling bias correction

1arc-daily
1994 - 2015

6 hydrological seasonal forecast

7 Performance evaluation

8 Mapping

Meteorological forcing's

Hydrological

Morphological, physical, soil, and land use properties

Observations

EFAS

Pegelportal

EMO – 1
Spatial resolution 1arcmin
Time resolution daily
Period 1990-2021

Seasonal forecast re-forecast

EFAS

Francesca Moschini; Margarita Choulga; Cinzia Mazzetti; Disperati, Juliana; Grimaldi, Stefania; Salamon, Peter; Prudhomme, Christel (2023): LISFLOOD static and parameter maps for Europe. European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) [Dataset] PID: <http://data.europa.eu/89h/f572c443-7466-4adf-87aa-c0847a169f23>

Pre-processor LISVAP

LISVAP Installed and tested in Levante HPC

1. Installing/initializing git for large file

```
git lfs install
```

2. clone LISVAP from the repository

```
git clone https://github.com/ec-jrc/lisflood-lisvap.git
```

```
cd lisflood-lisvap
```

3. Creating a conda environment for lisvap

```
conda create --name lisvap python=3.8 --no-default-packages
```

```
source activate lisvap
```

4. Installing and checking lisvap

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

5. Installing and checking pcraster

```
conda install -c conda-forge pcraster
```

6. Running LISVAP from scr folder

```
python lisvap1.py /my_system/lisflood-lisvap/tests/data/tests_efas.xml -v -t
```

```
#####
##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##
##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##
##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##
##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##
##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##
#####
TIP:
You can use $(ProjectDir) or $(ProjectPath) as built-in variable to use in this XML settings, to refer Lisvap project folder (in cas
You can use $(SettingsDir) or $(SettingsPath) to refer directory containing the XML settings.
-->
<lfsettings>
  <lfuser>
    <group>
      <comment>
        *****
        TIME-RELATED CONSTANTS
        *****
      </comment>
      <textvar name="CalendarDayStart" value="01/01/1995 00:00">
        <comment>
          calendar day number of 1st day in model run
          e.g. 1st of January: 1; 1st of June: 151 (or 152 in leap year)
        </comment>
      </textvar>
      <textvar name="DtSec" value="86400">
        <comment>
          time step [seconds] ALWAYS USE 86400!!
        </comment>
      </textvar>
      <textvar name="StepStart" value="01/01/1995 06:00">
        <comment>
          Number of first time step in simulation
        </comment>
      </textvar>
      <textvar name="StepEnd" value="31/12/1995 06:00">
        <comment>
          Number of last time step
        </comment>
      </textvar>
      <textvar name="ReportSteps" value="1..14">
        <comment>
          </comment>
      </comment>
    </group>
  </lfuser>
</lfsettings>
```


Hydrological Model LISFLOOD

LISFLOOD, LISFLOOD-Utilities and LISFLOOD-Calibration tools installed and tested in Levante HPC.

(Working in serie and in parallel).

```
# 2023-05-05 Installing Lisflood Calibration tool
# installation for solving the multiprocessing problems attemp 1

module load python3
module load git

conda create --name lisflood_calibration_2 python=3.7 -c conda-forge

git clone --single-branch https://github.com/ec-jrc/lisflood-calibration.git

source activate lisflood_calibration_2
conda install -c conda-forge pcraster gdal
pip install lisflood-model==4.1.2

# pip show lisflood-model # allows you to know where is the source code of lisflo
# /work/bb1245/hydromodelling/conda_venvs/lisflood_calibration_2/lib/python3.7/si
# After installing lisflood compile the cython module kinematic_wave_parallel_to
# To compile this Cython module to enable OpenMP multithreading (parallel kinemat
# Delete the files *.so (if any) in directory hydrological-modules
# Inside the hydrological_modules folder, execute "python compile_kinematic_wave_

# For get rid of the errors in related with hdf5
conda remove hdf5
conda install -c conda-forge hdf5==1.12.1

# other tools
pip install pandas
pip install numpy
pip install matplotlib
pip install netCDF4
pip install deap
conda install -c conda-forge deap

pip install -r requirements.txt # run it in the lisflood_code folder
pip install . # run it in the lisflood_calibration folder

pip install tbb # For parallelization
```

```
#####
##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##
##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##
##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##
##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##      ##
#####

<lfsettings>

<lfoptions>
#-----
# modelling and reporting options
#-----
<setoption choice="0" name="TemperatureInKelvin"/>
<setoption choice="1" name="gridSizeUserDefined"/>

# options to turn hydrological modules on/off
<setoption choice="0" name="cropsEPIC"/>

<setoption choice="1" name="wateruse"/>
<setoption choice="1" name="TransientWaterDemandChange"/>
<setoption choice="0" name="useWaterDemandAveYear"/>
<setoption choice="1" name="wateruseRegion"/>

<setoption choice="0" name="groundwaterSmooth"/>
<setoption choice="1" name="wateruseRegion"/>
<setoption choice="1" name="drainedIrrigation"/>
<setoption choice="1" name="riceIrrigation"/>
<setoption choice="0" name="indicator"/>

<setoption choice="1" name="openwaterevapo"/>
<setoption choice="0" name="simulateLakes"/>
<setoption choice="0" name="simulateReservoirs"/>

<setoption choice="0" name="simulateReservoirs"/>

<setoption choice="1" name="SplitRouting"/>

# use inflow data
<setoption choice="0" name="inflow"/>

# option to initialize Lisflood
<setoption choice="0" name="InitLisflood"/>
```


Calibration - Validation

Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm-II (NSGA-II)

Modified Kling-Gupta Efficiency

$$KGE' = 1 - \sqrt{(r - 1)^2 + (\beta - 1)^2 + (\gamma - 1)^2}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\sum_i x_i y_i - n \bar{x} \bar{y}}{\sqrt{\sum_i x_i^2 - n \bar{x}^2} \sqrt{\sum_i y_i^2 - n \bar{y}^2}}$$

$$\beta = \frac{\mu_s}{\mu_o} \quad \gamma = \frac{\sigma_s / \mu_s}{\sigma_o / \mu_o}$$

KGE'	Description
1.0 - 0.8	Very good
0.8 - 0.6	Good
0.6 - 0.4	Medium
0.4 - 0.2	Poor
< 0.2	Bad

Calibration - Validation

KGE'	Description
1.0 - 0.8	Excellent
0.8 - 0.6	Good
0.6 - 0.4	Acceptable
0.4 - 0.2	Low
< 0.2	very low

Calibration

Validation

Parameters maps for the study region

... a total of 14 maps

Dashboard

Hydrological seasonal forecast

DAKI-FWS

Catchments of interest

Hydrograph

List of catchments

Select...

Clicked Point 7.184211526660529, 50.54654466503386

Selected catchment: None

Information about the calibration

Flow duration curve

Observed period

Probability of exceedence

Forecast period

(12.47, 65.30) means $pr(Q > 65.30 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}) = 12.78 \%$

(p, q) means $pr(Q > q) = p$

SCEWERO

3. Example – DAKI

Lon = 10.063°
Lat = 52.622°

STRENGTHENING THE RESEARCH CAPACITIES FOR EXTREME WEATHER EVENTS IN ROMANIA

113m³/s

28.31 m³/s

2.8 m³/s

- $Q_{max} = 113 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$
- $Q_{mean} = 28.31 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$
- $Q_{min} = 2.83 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$

UNIVERSITATEA BABEŞ-BOLYAI

Universiteit Antwerpen

3. Example – DAKI

Temperature

Wind speed

Streamflows

Ticks

Propagation of the Ahrtal flood in 2021

Cumulative rainfall in the region:

Müsch

Altenahr

Bad Dodendorf

Observed precipitation and water level

SCEWERO

4. Operating FEWS

STRENGTHENING THE RESEARCH CAPACITIES FOR EXTREME WEATHER EVENTS IN ROMANIA

Global Flood Awareness System - GLOFAS

<https://global-flood.emergency.copernicus.eu/>

European Flood Awareness System - EFAS

<https://european-flood.emergency.copernicus.eu/en>

AI – Google Flood Hub

<https://g.co/floodhub>

Nearing, G., Cohen, D., Dube, V. *et al.* Global prediction of extreme floods in ungauged watersheds. *Nature* **627**, 559–563 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07145-1>

Nevo, S., *et al.* Flood forecasting with machine learning models in an operational framework, *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.*, **26**, 4013–4032, <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-26-4013-2022>, 2022.

Hydrological cycle

Hydrological modelling

Models

Protocol

Application

Thank you!

Questions ?

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Hands on: Hydrological modelling

1. Define model goals

Somes-Tisa Watershed Area

Somes-Tisa watershed area is located to the North and North-Western part of the country, being delineated to the North by the natural border – Tisa river with Ukraine on a length of 61 km, to the West by the border with the Hungarian Republic, and on the national territory, it borders on Siret Basin to the East, Mures Basin to the South and Crisuri Basin to the South-West.

<https://inundatii.ro/en/river-basins/somes-tisa-watershed-area/>

Flood records

The maximum quantities of precipitations are recorded during spring-summer, in particular during the period March-June and in August. One can remember several maximum historical values of precipitations occurred during serious floods across the entire river basin as those recorded in May 1970 (over 150 mm/24 hours and even 200 mm/24 hours in Baia Sprie).

Serious floods, with significant maximum discharges, come from rainfalls recorded on large areas of the basin or from mixed source (snowmelt and rain). The maximum historical flood over the last 50-60 years was that occurred in 1970, having a mixed source. An analysis of the series of floods over around the last 50 years shows that the most significant floods occurred in: 1970, 1974, 1975, 1978, 1979, 1980, 1981, 1989, 1993, 1995, 1998, 2000, 2001, 2005 and 2008.

The first half of 1970 was characterized by catastrophic floods. The most serious floods occurred on the rivers Someș, Tisa, Tur, Vișeu, Iza, Lapus, Sieu, Crasna, Almas, Someșul Mic and their tributaries. Discharges exceeding the insurance of 1% were recorded on the rivers Someș (downstream Dej) and Vișeu, on the other water courses, there were discharges recorded with the insurance ranging between 5– 10%. There was a breach of dikes on rivers Someș and Tur (Satu Mare county), which caused the flooding of many urban and rural localities. Floods were caused by long-lasting heavy rainfalls accompanied by snowmelt resulting in floods that exceeded the flood level, on most rivers in Someș-Tisa river basin. Important urban localities were affected, such as Nasaud, Beclean, Gherla, Dej, Zalău, Jibou, Simleu, Satu Mare, as well as many rural localities (over 200).

<https://inundatii.ro/en/river-basins/somes-tisa-watershed-area/>

Floods

Meteorological forcings

https://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ftp/jrc-opendata/CEMS-EFAS/meteorological_forcings/EMO-1arcmin/

Discharge

<https://portal.grdc.bafg.de/applications/public.html?publicuser=PublicUser#dataDownload/Stations>

Geographical information

DEM 30 meter resolution

1arcmin EFAS

https://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ftp/jrc-opendata/CEMS-EFAS/LISFLOOD_static_and_parameter_maps_for_EFAS/

<https://inundatii.ro/en/river-basins/somes-tisa-watershed-a>

<https://aquaticcedynamics.github.io/hydrology-workbook/E5.html>

Extreme events

Gumbel Distribution

Return period Tr [Years]	Streamflow Q [m ³ /s]
1.5	610
2	736
5	1048
10	1254
25	1515
50	1708
100	1900
200	2091
500	2343
1000	2534

Flow duration curves

Hydrological model

GR4J

Si $P_k \geq E$, alors $P_n = P_k - E$ et $E_n = 0$,
 Si $P_k < E$, alors $P_n = 0$ et $E_n = E - P_k$

$$Ps = \frac{X1 \cdot \left(1 - \left(\frac{S_k}{X1}\right)^2\right) \cdot \tanh\left(\frac{P_n}{X1}\right)}{1 + \frac{S_k}{X1} \cdot \tanh\left(\frac{P_n}{X1}\right)} \quad \text{et} \quad Es = \frac{S_k \cdot \left(2 - \frac{S_k}{X1}\right) \cdot \tanh\left(\frac{E_n}{X1}\right)}{1 + \left(1 - \frac{S_k}{X1}\right) \cdot \tanh\left(\frac{E_n}{X1}\right)}$$

$$S' = S_k + Ps - Es,$$

$$Perc = S' \cdot \left\{ 1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{4}{9} \cdot \frac{S'}{X1} \right)^4 \right]^{-1} \right\}, \quad S_{k+1} = S' - Perc$$

$$Perc + (P_n - P_s)$$

$$\text{Si } 0 \leq j \leq X_4, SH1(j) = \left(\frac{j}{X_4}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}; \quad \text{Si } j > X_4, SH1(j) = 1$$

$$\text{Si } 0 \leq j \leq X_4, SH2(j) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{j}{X_4}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}};$$

$$\text{Si } X_4 \leq j \leq 2X_4, SH2(j) = 1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(2 - \frac{j}{X_4}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}};$$

$$\text{Si } j > 2X_4, SH2(j) = 1$$

$$UH1(j) = SH1(j) - SH1(j-1)$$

$$UH2(j) = SH2(j) - SH2(j-1)$$

$$Q9(k) = 0.9 \cdot \sum_{j=1}^k UH1(j) \cdot Pr(k-j+1),$$

$$Q1(k) = 0.1 \cdot \sum_{j=1}^m UH2(j) \cdot Pr(k-j+1)$$

$$F = X2 \cdot \left(\frac{R_k}{X3}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}; \quad R' = \max(0; R_k + Q9(k) + F)$$

$$(DP) \begin{cases} Qr = R' \cdot \left\{ 1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{R'}{X3} \right)^4 \right]^{-1} \right\}; & R_{k+1} = R' - Qr \\ Qd = \max(0; Q1(k) + F); \\ Q(k) = Qr + Qd \end{cases}$$

- X1 Capacity of the production store (mm)
- X2 Water exchange coefficient (mm)
- X3 Capacity of the nonlinear routing store (mm)
- X4 Unit hydrograph time base (day)

Perrin, C., Michel, C., & Andréassian, V. (2003). Improvement of a parsimonious model for streamflow simulation. *Journal of Hydrology*, 279(1-4), 275-289. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694\(03\)00225-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694(03)00225-7)

Implementation in python

```
import numpy as np
...
This class modelate a process rainfall-runoff
Perrin, C., C. Michel, et al. (2003). "Improvement of a parsimonious model for streamflow simul
http://www.cemagref.fr/webgr/Modelesgb/gr4j/fonctionnement_gr4jgb.htm
...

class GR4J:
    'Class hydrological model GR4J'

    def __init__(self, PEQ, A, X, S0, R0):
        self.set_PEQ(PEQ)
        self.a = np.copy(A) # Area of basin in km2
        n = PEQ.shape[0] # Get the lenght of data series
        self.X = np.copy(X) # Parameters of model
        self.Pn = np.zeros((n))
        self.En = np.zeros((n))
        self.R_ = np.copy(R0)
        self.S_ = np.copy(S0)

    # Define the inputs
    def set_PEQ(self, PEQ):
        self.P = np.copy(PEQ[:,1])
        self.E = np.copy(PEQ[:,2])
        self.Q = np.copy(PEQ[:,3])
```

<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/seasonal-original-single-levels?tab=overview>

Meteorological forcings

The screenshot shows the Copernicus Climate Data Store interface. At the top, there are logos for the European Union, Copernicus, and ECMWF. The main navigation bar includes 'Climate Data Store', 'Datasets', 'Applications', 'User guide', and 'Live'. A user profile for 'Edgar Espitia' is visible in the top right. Below the navigation, there is a banner for a forum announcement dated 26 Sep 2024. The breadcrumb trail indicates the current location: 'Home > Datasets > Seasonal forecast daily and subdaily data on single levels'. The main heading is '★ Seasonal forecast daily and subdaily data on single levels'. Below this, there are four tabs: 'Overview', 'Download', 'Quality', and 'Documentation'. The 'Overview' tab is active, displaying a text description: 'This entry covers single-level data and soil-level data at the original time resolution (once a day, or once every 6 hours, depending on the variable)'. To the right of the text is a circular diagram showing data sources (ECMWF, Met Office, METEO FRANCE, DWD, CMCC) feeding into the 'Climate Change Service'. On the far right, there is a 'Quality Assurance' sidebar with expandable sections for 'Data Management', 'Data records', 'Metadata', and 'Documentation'. A small red circular icon is located at the bottom right of the sidebar.

Model calibration

Based on: Shen, H., Tolson, B. A., & Mai, J. (2022). Time to Update the Split-Sample Approach in Hydrological Model Calibration. *Water Resources Research*, 58(3), e2021WR031523. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021WR031523>

Model calibration

$$KGE^c = 1 - \sqrt{(r - 1)^2 + (\beta - 1)^2 + (\gamma - 1)^2}$$

$$r_{OS} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O}) (S_i - \bar{S})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - \bar{S})^2}}$$

bias ratio

$$\beta = \frac{\mu_s}{\mu_o}$$

Variability ratio

$$\gamma = \frac{\sigma_s / \mu_s}{\sigma_o / \mu_o}$$

	KGE'	Description
	0.8 - 1.0	Excellent
	0.6 - 0.8	Good
	0.4 - 0.6	Acceptable
	0.2 - 0.4	Low
	< 0.2	Very low

	r
	0.8 - 1.0
	0.6 - 0.8
	0.4 - 0.6
	0.2 - 0.4
	< 0.2

	bias ratio β
	> 1.5
	1.3 - 1.5
	1.1 - 1.3
	0.9 - 1.1
	0.7 - 0.9
	0.5 - 0.7
	< 0.5

	variability ratio γ
	> 1.5
	1.3 - 1.5
	1.1 - 1.3
	0.9 - 1.1
	0.7 - 0.9
	0.5 - 0.7
	< 0.5

Model calibration

Flow duration curves

Flow Duration Curve - Calibration period

Flow Duration Curve Validation period

Scatter plots

Testing

Testing

Flow Duration Curve - Calibration period

Q obs vs Q sim cal period

Short term flood summary

<https://global-flood.emergency.copernicus.eu/>

Seasonal forecast

Seasonal forecast

Climatological thresholds
From extreme low to extreme high (red to blue), derived from range-dependent model climatologies

Ensemble forecast boxplot

Seasonal Outlook - Reporting Points

Point Information

Point ID	Station ID	Country	Basin	River	Station Name	Drainage Area [km ²]	Longitude [Deg]	Latitude [Deg]	USFLOOD Drainage Area [km ²]	USFLOOD X [Deg]	USFLOOD Y [Deg]
SH236026	G0444	Germany	Danube	Danube	Ingolstadt	20001	11.4220	48.7540	20419	11.4250	48.7750

Seasonal hydrograph of antecedent, climatological and forecast information

Anomaly category		Rank	Description
Extreme low		1-10	Bottom 10% of the climatological distribution
Low		10-25	15% from the 1 st decile to the 1 st quartile
Bit low	Near normal (25-75)	25-40	15% from the 1 st quartile to the 2 nd quintile
Normal		40-60	20% from the 2 nd quintile to the 3 rd quintile
Bit high		60-75	15% from the 3 rd quintile to the 3 rd quartile
High		75-90	15% from the 3 rd quartile to the 9 th decile
Extreme high		90-100	Top 10% of the climatological distribution

Seasonal forecast

Uncertainty category	Rank STD	Description
Low uncertainty	<10	The standard deviation of the ensemble member ranks is less than 10
Medium uncertainty	10-20	The standard deviation of the ensemble member ranks is between 10 and 20
High uncertainty	20<	The standard deviation of the ensemble member ranks is higher than 20

Seasonal forecast probability (numbers) and expected anomaly category (coloured cells) [2025-07-01]

	July 2025						August 2025						September 2025						October 2025						November 2025						December 2025						January 2026												
	EL	L	BL	N	BH	H	EH	EL	L	BL	N	BH	H	EH	EL	L	BL	N	BH	H	EH	EL	L	BL	N	BH	H	EH	EL	L	BL	N	BH	H	EH	EL	L	BL	N	BH	H	EH	EL	L	BL	N	BH	H	EH
July 2025	65	27	4	0	2	2	0	33	31	12	10	8	4	2	16	29	16	15	8	8	8	23	10	18	23	12	12	2	10	19	16	27	12	14	2	14	16	17	12	10	23	8	12	10	16	21	12	23	6
June 2025	22	21	14	21	14	2	6	14	31	19	16	10	6	4	12	14	18	17	16	17	6	17	14	14	19	14	12	10	16	17	12	23	14	6	12	8	19	12	19	20	14	8							
May 2025	12	23	16	21	20	8	0	12	21	14	21	10	16	6	6	14	14	33	17	10	6	18	16	17	21	14	8	6	16	14	14	10	19	25	2														
April 2025	12	12	19	14	21	12	10	8	12	16	14	21	19	10	6	19	18	23	8	10	16	12	15	21	14	12	14	12																					
March 2025	6	21	14	12	19	20	8	6	14	21	20	16	19	4	4	21	16	27	12	16	4																												
February 2025	10	15	14	25	14	16	6	6	12	14	27	19	6	16																																			
January 2025	8	12	18	14	25	17	6																																										

Seasonal forecast download

<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets>

The screenshot shows the Copernicus Climate Data Store (ADS) interface. At the top, there are logos for the European Union, Copernicus, Climate Change Service, and ECMWF. The user 'Edgar Espitia' is logged in. The main navigation includes 'Climate Data Store', 'Datasets', 'Applications', 'User guide', and 'Live'. A search bar contains the text 'discharge', and the results show 4 items, with 0 on ADS and 10 on EWDS. The first result is 'Multi-model seasonal forecasts of river discharge for Europe from January 2021 to present', updated 7 days ago. The description states: 'This dataset provides hydrological seasonal forecasts of monthly mean river discharge across Europe. Two hydrological model ensembles are provided. The first is an E-HYPE multi-model system comprising eight model realisations using a catchment-based resolution. The second comprises the E-HYPEgrid, V...'

Thank you!

Questions ?